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CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF UKRAINIAN FILM AND TELEVISION DIRECTOR V. HORPENKO

The purpose of the article is to analyse the creative activity in audiovisual art and production of Ukrainian film and TV director, actor, teacher of screen arts, Doctor of Arts, Professor, Academician of the Higher School Academy Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko. **Research methodology** is based on applying the personological method, the method of the theory of individuality and the historical-biographical one. These approaches allow the researcher to collect and analyze the unknown or little-known facts about Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko's creative activity in screen arts. **Conclusions.** Concluding the aforementioned, it can be stated that the scientific objectives have been accomplished: personal life and career of Ukrainian film and television director V. Horpenko have been studied; his advent to cinematography has been described; the reasons why V. Horpenko refused to shoot the feature film «Nina» with O. Shvachko have been analysed; the situation

formed at the time of work on the film after the same name science fiction novel by the Struhatsky brothers «Hard to be a God» has been described; the directing work of V. Horpenko on Ukrainian television has been mentioned. Nevertheless, **the prospects** for scientific research remain promising, as V. Horpenko continues active work in the sphere of audiovisual art and production, as well as pedagogy of screen arts of Ukraine. **The significance** of this research in terms of Art History lies within discovering and introducing the new important facts about creative activity in audiovisual art and production of Ukrainian film and television director, actor, teacher of screen arts, Doctor of Arts, Professor, Academician of the Higher School Academy Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko.

Key words: Volodymyr Horpenko, cinema, television, creative activity, pedagogy of screen arts, Kyiv Film Studios.

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Творча діяльність українського режисера кіно і телебачення В. Г. Горпенка

Мета статті. Дослідити та проаналізувати творчу діяльність в аудіовізуальному мистецтві й виробництві українського режисера кіно і телебачення, актора, педагога екранних мистецтв, доктора мистецтвознавства, професора, дійсного члена (академіка) Академії вищої школи Володимира Григоровича Горпенка. **Методологія дослідження** полягає у застосуванні методів персонології, теорії

особистості й історико-біографічного методу. Зазначені методологічні підходи дозволяють зібрати й дослідити невідомі та маловідомі факти із життя і творчої діяльності режисера кіно і телебачення, актора В. Горпенка. **Висновки.** Підсумовуючи вищевикладене, можна зазначити, що поставлені наукові завдання виконані: досліджено життєвий і творчий шлях українського режисера кіно і телебачення В. Г. Горпенка; описано його прихід у кінематогра,; проаналізовано причини відмови В. Г. Горпенка від зйомок кінострічки «Ніна» з О. Ф. Швачком; описано ситуацію, що склалася під час роботи над фільмом за однойменною науково-фантастичною повістю братів Стругацьких «Важко бути Богом»; згадано про режисерську роботу В. Г. Горпенка на українському телебаченні. Тим не менш, **перспективи** наукових досліджень залишаються великими, оскільки В. Г. Горпенко продовжує активно працювати в аудіовізуальному мистецтві й виробництві та педагогіці екранних мистецтв України. **Значення** цього дослідження для мистецтвознавства полягає у віднайденні та введенні в науковий обіг здобутий автором новий цінний фактаж про творчу діяльність в аудіовізуальному мистецтві і виробництві українського режисера кіно і телебачення, актора, педагога екранних мистецтв, доктора мистецтвознавства, професора, дійсного члена (академіка) Академії вищої школи Володимира Григоровича Горпенка.

Ключові слова: Володимир Горпенко, кінематограф, телебачення, творча діяльність, педагогіка екранних мистецтв, Київська кіностудія художніх фільмів.

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Творческая деятельность украинского режиссера кино и телевидения В. Г. Горпенко

Цель статьи. Исследовать и проанализировать творческую деятельность в аудиовизуальном искусстве и производстве украинского режиссера кино и телевидения, актера, педагога экранных искусств, доктора искусствоведения, профессора, действительного члена (академика) Академии высшей школы Владимира Григорьевича Горпенко. **Методология исследования** заключается в применении методов персонологии, теории личности и историко-биографического метода. Отмеченные методологические подходы позволяют собрать и исследовать неизвестные и малоизвестные факты из жизни и творческой деятельности режиссера кино и телевидения, актера В. Горпенко. **Выводы.** Подытоживая вышеизложенное, можно отметить, что поставленные научные задания выполнены: исследован жизненный и творческий путь украинского режиссера кино и телевидения В. Г. Горпенко; описан его приход в кинематограф; проанализированы причины отказа В. Г. Горпенко от съемок киноленты «Нина» с А. Ф. Швачко; описана ситуация, сложившаяся во время работы над фильмом по одноименной научно-фантастической повести братьев Стругацких «Трудно быть Богом»; упомянуто о режиссерской работе В. Г. Горпенко на

украинском телевидении. Тем не менее, **перспективы** научных исследований остаются высокими, поскольку В. Г. Горпенко продолжает активно работать в аудиовизуальном искусстве и производстве, а также в педагогике экранных искусств Украины. **Значимость** этого исследования для искусствоведения заключается в нахождении и введении в научное обращение добытый автором новый ценный фактаж о творческой деятельности в аудиовизуальном искусстве и производстве украинского режиссера кино и телевидения, актера, педагога экранных искусств, доктора искусствоведения, профессора, действительного члена (академика) Академии высшей школы Владимира Григорьевича Горпенко.

Ключевые слова: Владимир Горпенко, кинематограф, телевидение, творческая деятельность, педагогика экранных искусств, Киевская киностудия художественных фильмов

Problem setting. The significance of this research is based on the need to study the creative activity of the leading representatives of Ukrainian culture and science, including Ukrainian film and TV director, film expert, screen arts specialist, Doctor of Arts, holder of two degrees (in «Theory and History of Culture» and «Cinematographic Arts, Television»), the only Doctor of Arts in Ukraine with a degree in «Cinematographic Arts, Television», Professor, Academician of the Higher School Academy, member of the National Union of Cinematographers of Ukraine Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko (born 3.07.1941, v. Bulhaki, Zhytomyr reg., Ukraine), who turned 75 years old in 2016.

The purpose of the article. To analyze the creative activity in audiovisual art and production of Ukrainian film and television director, actor, teacher of screen arts, Doctor of Arts, Professor, Academician of The Higher School Academy Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko.

Analysis of the latest researches and publications. Scientific, creative and mediapedagogic activity of famous Ukrainian film and television director, film critic, teacher of screen arts, Doctor of Arts, Professor, Academician of The Higher School Academy, member of the National Union of Cinematographers of Ukraine Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko had such teachers as I. Zubavyna [5], S. Trymbach [7], I. Zhuravel [4], O. Bezruchko [1] etc. However, regarding the scale of his contribution into Ukrainian screen arts pedagogy and film studies, the new research is really important.

The scientific objective of this article is the research into personal life and career of Ukrainian film and television director V. Horpenko; the description of his advent to cinematography; analysis of reasons why V. Horpenko refused to shoot the feature film «Nina» with O. Shvachko; the description the situation formed at the time of work on the film after the same name science fiction novel by the Struhatsky brothers «Hard to be a God»; recollection of the directing work by V. Horpenko on Ukrainian television.

Methods of research. To accomplish the scientific objectives the protagonists of the research were interviewed; all the available literature was reviewed and analysed; Ukrainian archives (The Central State Archive-Museum of Literature and Arts of Ukraine, archives of Kyiv National University of Television, archives of Kyiv National University

of Theatre, Film and Television named after Karpenko-Karyi, The Museum-Archive of Oleksandr Dovzhenko National Film Studio, etc.) were studied; specialized Ukrainian and Russian newspapers and journals: «Za Radianskyi Film», «Iskusstvo Kino», «Kinovedcheskije Zapiski», «Novyny Kinoekranu», «Kino-Kolo», «Kino-Teatr» etc.

Research methodology is based on applying the personological method, the method of the theory of individuality and the historical-biographical one. These approaches allow the researcher to collect and analyze the unknown or little-known facts about Volodymyr Hryhorovych Horpenko's creative activity in screen arts.

Exposition of the basic material. Volodymyr Horpenko started his creative career as an actor after he had graduated from school. During one theatre season since September 1958 till 1959, he worked as a supportive actor at Zhytomyr Ukrainian Music and Drama Theatre.

On June 27, 1959 Volodymyr Horpenko entered the acting faculty of State Institute of Theatre Art named after Karpenko-Karyi. On the third year of studies, he asked if he could attend lectures on film directing by the leading theatre teacher, supporter of Les Kurbas Mykhailo Poliiievktovych Verkhatskyi, who appealed to the principal I. Chabanenko with a request to transfer the student to the newly opened film faculty. Horpenko was invited to the principal, who raised his head, looked at him and said nothing.

After he got back after holidays on February 27, 1962 he saw the order about his transfer to the workshop by V. Ivchenko. The student asked Verkhatskyi indignantly: «Why did you do that to me?»

The wise professor answered as follows: «What can I do if your path goes in that direction?»

Having looked at the timetable, Horpenko went to the film studio, where he met one of the founders of the film faculty, the well-known Ukrainian theatre and film director, honoured artist of the USSR (1960), laureate of Taras Shevchenko state prize of the USSR (1967) Viktor Ilarionovych Ivchenko (09.11.1912, Bohodukhiv, Kharkiv reg. – 05.09.1972, Kyiv).

The master asked: «Who are you?»

Horpenko answered: «Your student».

Ivchenko lowered his head saying nothing. Within half a year of relations between the master and his student, who had entered the course on film directing without master's preliminary approval, were not easy – Viktor Ivchenko had a stern temper... But his educational gift and human integrity multiplied by fatherly good nature quickly got better. The talented young man soon became a legitimate student of the first joint film directing and acting course. The master and his student never regretted this choice. Horpenko devoted the article «Lessons gained on the way. To the 70th anniversary of V. Ivchenko» to his teacher [3], remembering him warmly at all Ivchenko and his students commemoration meetings [2].

After graduating from Ukraine's first joint workshop of directors of feature films and film actors, organized by Ivchenko at the newly founded film faculty of State Institute of Theatre Art named after Karpenko-Karyi (now – Institute of Screen Arts of Kyiv National

I. K. Theatre, Cinema and Television University named after Karpenko-Karyi) V. Horpenko defended his thesis by short TV film «Two deaths».

After that Volodymyr Horpenko attained an honorary creative work referral to Kyiv Feature Film Studio named after O.P Dovzhenko (now – Oleksandr Dovzhenko National Film Studio). The young film director allowed no compromises: if the quality of the feature film was not satisfactory for him, he could reject the work. So, Horpenko in 1970 understood that the joint work on film «Nina» with Oleksii Philimonovych Shvachko (18.01.1901, v. Chepilky, Cherkasy reg. – 28.03.1988, Kyiv) was going to be archaic. That is why he went to the head of film studio and rejected the first film he produced. That was a very brave step, as Shvachko was one of the oldest Ukrainian directors who directed «Martin Borulia» (1953, together with H. Yura), «Earth» (1954, together with A. Buchma), «Kids of Sun» (1956), «Bloody Sunrise» (1956), «Morale of Miss Dulska» (1957, together with L. Varpakhovskiy), «Rockets shall never start» (1954, together with A. Timoshynin), «Spies» (1968, together with I. Samborskyi). Vitalii Kondratov worked with Oleksii Shvachko on the feature film «Nina» instead of Volodymyr Horpenko.

Horpenko proved his professional competency – he was appointed independent director of the film «Laurels». He was awarded with a diploma for the best directing work at Film Festival in Zhdaniv (1973).

In 1979 Volodymyr Horpenko as a producer together with Mykhailo Reznikovych shot a two-part TV film «Rain in an unfamiliar city» (132 minutes) after the novel by Daniil Hranin, who also wrote the screenplay. This film starred well-known Ukrainian and Soviet actors:

Henadii Frolov, Liudmyla Zaitseva, Mykola Penkov, Raisa Kurkina, Valentyna Ananina, Mykola Rushkovskiy, Liudmyla Chincevaia, Heorhii Kishko and others. Operator of this film was Naum Slutskiy, artist-producer – Victor Myhulko, composer – Mikhael Taryverdiev.

According to the plot of the film, the engineer Chizhehov went on a business trip to a small country town, where he got acquainted with Kira. Warm feelings emerged between those elderly people.

In 1980 Volodymyr Horpenko was the film director of the seven-part TV feature film (490 minutes) «Courage», the producer of which was Boris Ivanovych Savchenko. The film with the screenplay by Oleksandr Shlepianov was about the construction of the city of Komsomolsk-on-Amur in 1932. This film starred Volodymyr Antonyk, Natalia Andreichenko, Olena Drapeko, Oleksandr Halibin, Oleksandr Kavalero, Valerii Ivchenko.

In 1981 Horpenko worked as a film director on the full-length feature film «Yaroslav Mudryi» (156 minutes), the producer of which was the laureate of the state prize of the USSR (1978), honoured artist (1981) Hryhorii Romanovych Kokhan (23.06.1931, v. Bortkov, Lviv reg. – 03.01.2014, Kyiv). In this historical film the time of son of King Volodymyr – Yaroslav, nicknamed Yaroslav the Wise, is described. The struggle against external and internal enemies evolved in parallel with the plotline of prince's love to a plain girl called Liubava. The roles in this film were played by such well-known Ukrainian and Soviet actors as Yurii Muravytskyi, Petro Veliaminov, Liudmyla Smorodina, Kostiantyn Stepankov, Oleh Drach, Leonid Filatov, Mykola Belyi, Mykola Babenko, Vsevolod Havrilov, Boris Stavytskyi, Olga Belianska,

Andrii Kharytonov, Mykola Hrynko, Vaclav Dvorzhecky. Authors of the screenplay were Pavlo Zahrebelnyi, Mykhailo Veprinskyi, Hryhorii Kokhan; operator – Felix Hilevych; artists-producers – Viktor and Larysa Zhilko; composer – Evhenii Stankovych. In 1982 the film «Yaroslav Mudryi» was awarded with a prize and a diploma from the jury for historical films at All-Union Film Festival in Tallinn.

That was the only work by V. Horpenko with H. Kokhan – in 1984 they worked on four-part TV feature film «Acceleration» after the novel by Pavlo Zahrebelnyi «Boost». The film is constructed as a retrospective of the major film character's recollections – a head of science research institute, scientist-cyberneticist Petro Karnal – about his military youth and life partners, which became a reason for his meeting with a journalist called Anastasia. The film starred such famous actors as Petro Veliaminov, Igor Yankovskyi, Rostislav Yankovskiy, Volodymyr Yankovskyi, Farida Myminova, Nelli Pshenna, Vadym Ledohorov, Oleh Vavilov, Mykola Rushkovskiy, Mykola Zadniprovskiy, Natalia Panchik, Serhii Varchuk, Mykola Hrynko, Oleksandr Bystrushkin, Kateryna Krupennikova. Authors of the screenplay were Pavlo Zahrebelnyi, Mykhailo Reznikovych, Hryhorii Kokhan; operators – Felix Hilevych, Arkadii Pershin; artist-producer – Yurii Myller, composer – Evhenii Stankovych.

In 1984 Volodymyr Horpenko was forced to accept the director's position in the feature film «Your Peaceful Sky», having replaced one of the first Ukrainian film directors, graduate of Kyiv State Institute of Cinematography (1935) Isaak Petrovych Shmaruk (22.08.1910 – 02.08.1986), who had been taken to hospital with infarct just before the

start of shooting process. Volodymyr Horpenko was requested to lead the film under the only condition of not changing the film crew. The film was shot without any changes in actors cast and film crew. The roles in the film were played by such well-known Ukrainian and Soviet actors as Emanuel Vitorhan, Liudmyla Yaroshenko, Kostiantyn Stepankov, Vasyl Korzun, Mykola Dupak, Valerii Tsvietkov, Badry Kakabadze, Serhii Pidhornyi, Oleksandr Movchan, Henadii Bolotov, Masha Slidovker, Mykola Hudz, and Volodymyr Horpenko.

According to the plot, in terms of «defence film» times, engineer Mykhailo Samarin, a head of construction bureau, was assigned with a difficult task – to accelerate the works on the creation of air-defence missile system «Zaslon», which was intended to stand against the new American first strike weapon bomber «Blow». Author of the screenplay was Oleksandr Bilaiev, operator – Oleksii Prokopenko, artist-producer – Heorhii Prokopets, composer – Mark Fradkin, with lyrics by Robert Rozhdiestvienskyi.

After the beginning of the period of «restructuring» in the USSR filmmakers attained a possibility to make joint projects not only with experts of the Soviet regime. So, in 1988–1989 Volodymyr Horpenko worked with the German director Piter Fleischman on the film «Hard to be a God», based on the same name science fiction novel by the Struhatsky brothers.

Because film director Oleh Borysovyh Fialko (born 28.06.1946, Druzhkivka, Donetsk reg.) had rejected this work, so much had to be done by Volodymyr Horpenko in this problematic fellowship. This was unordinary but quite useful experience. The peculiarities of the work on

this project were described by V. Horpenko in the interview given to the author of the research.

One of the authors of the screenplay and producer from the German side, Piter Fleischman, brought a fully-developed screenplay, exposure sheet etc. Having looked through the material, Horpenko noted that 450 meters were odd – there were special experts invited to improve plot lines with the help of computer. Horpenko also questioned the decoration schemes made by German artists. Afterwards Ukrainian artists were invited to make sketches in a very tight schedule. They constructed fantastic decorations for the film on Yalta film set. It is a pleasure to note the fact that their sketches have been saved in Hollywood as an example of wonderful work.

Finally, they managed to reapprove the actors and amend the screenplay. But, as it turned out on the first shooting day, the vision of the film by Peter Fleischman could not guarantee the high opinion quality of both Horpenko and the major actor performing the role of Rumata, Hollywood star Bill Peterson. Horpenko remembers his words: «I'm not so big a star to play in a bad film». V. Horpenko in front of Radinfilm and Bill Peterson in front of British insurance company raised the issue of replacing Peter Fleischman. The shooting was stopped, a representative of the company Completion Bond, who had exclusive legal rights to change producers, also came to the conclusion that the change was necessary. Removing Fleischman from the producer's post was a difficult thing because of the skilfully written contract, which made the procedure impossible.

After two weeks of idle time, Peter Fleischman, having paid a huge penalty to the company, not only stayed a production director as well as producer, but also invited art director J. Gofman. As a protest, Volodymyr Horpenko and Bill Peterson refused to take part in the work on the film. This joint project of the FRG and the USSR involved such well-known German and Soviet actors as: Edvard Zentara, Oleksandr Philipenko, Ann Gotye, Kristina Kayfman, Andrii Boltnev, Pier Klimenty, Hugo Kvester, Verner Khercog, Mykhailo Hlyzkyi, Elgudzha Burduli, Angelika Tomas, Lev Perfilov, Ilia Ivanov, Mykhailo Kramar, Rehimantas Adomaitis, Brigit Dol', Tomas Shyukke, Markus Orf, Arnis Licitis, Yurii Nesheretnyi, Ivan Herasevych, Vadym Kaporikov, Nina Il'ina, Viacheslav Hanenko, Henadii Khrapunkov, Oleh Isaev, Serhii Oziranyi, Henadii Ivanov.

A group of artists worked over the screenplay: Piter Fleischman, Jean-Claude Karer, Dal Orlpov, Bert Vaynshenker, Valentyna Rydvanova. In this film there were a few operators: Pavlo Lebeshev, Claus Myuller-Laye, Ezhi Hostik, Oleksii Zolotarev, Oleksandr Shihaev, Tomas Maykh, Oksana Medvid and Serhii Khotymskyi were artists-producers, and Yurgen Fritc – composer.

Together with his active engagement in cinematography, V. Horpenko also worked on Ukrainian TV – amidst the 1990s he shot a triptych of video films «Who are we?», which was broadcast by the National Television Company of Ukraine during many years in the program of celebrations of the Independence day of Ukraine. The author of the article, at that time student of Kyiv State Institute of Theatre, played an episodic role in it. Triptych was acknowledged as the best

video film of All-Ukrainian festival of television programs «Ukraine – wonderful wonder».

During all his creative career V. Horpenko dedicated himself to the art paradigm of his teacher V. Ivchenko, who was sure that each film must be an invention: «This is possible under the only condition: when a new film and a new role are undertaken by an artist...This notion of an artist includes a lot of constituent parts: talent, own vision of the world, integrity of artistic positions, genteelness of ideas, fine executive skills... That is why I will always repeat to my students: coming up to the shooting set is a great responsibility in front of the people» [6, p. 22].

Conclusions. Concluding the aforementioned, it can be stated that the scientific objectives have been accomplished: personal life and career of Ukrainian film and television director V. Horpenko have been studied; his advent to cinematography has been described; the reasons why V. Horpenko refused to shoot the feature film «Nina» with O. Shvachko have been analysed; the situation formed at the time of work on the film after the same name science fiction novel by the Struhatsky brothers «Hard to be a God» has been described; the directing work of V. Horpenko on Ukrainian television has been mentioned.

Nevertheless, **the prospects** for scientific research remain promising, as V. Horpenko continues active work in the sphere of audiovisual art and production, as well as pedagogy of screen arts of Ukraine.

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